
Study-based Systematic Mapping Analysis of Cloud Technologies for Leveraging IT Resource and Service Management: The Case Study of the Science Gateway Approach

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Abstract Currently, there is a proliferation of technological tools with a Science Gateway approach. For IT administrators manage these kinds of tools is not a trivial activity, although there is a significant volume of related studies. This situation represents a latent challenge to IT administrators in TERS (Technology Ecosystem for Research Support). This paper analyzes and classifies studies related to IT resources and services management applicable to this type of

technology ecosystem. Methodologically we used an adaptation of guidelines aimed at the construction of a SMS (Systematic Mapping Study). Additionally, we performed an analysis of the papers to recognize inferences and trends in them, which allowed us to claim that cloud computing technology plays a predominant role. We consider it good practice for implementations that support research processes. In this sense, we recommend to those interested in this topic to prioritize cloud technologies to achieve an adequate management of the set of IT resources and services used to support Science Gateway environments.

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1 Introduction

Computer technology has played a significant role as a support element in scientific advances. This technology has specialized to the point of consolidating conceptually in various terms such as (a) Cyberinfrastructure defined as “the integration of computing hardware, software, and network technology, along with data, information management, and human resources to advance scholarship and research” [1–3]. (b) eScience, widely accepted in Europe and defined as “Computationally intensive science carried out through distributed global collaborations enabled by the Internet, involving access to large data

collections, very large scale computing resources and high-performance visualization” [2]. And (c) Research Infrastructures defined as “resources and services that are used by the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields. They include major scientific equipment (or sets of instruments), knowledge-based resources such as collections, archives, and scientific data, e-infrastructures, such as data and computing systems and communication networks, and any other tools that are essential to achieve excellence in research and innovation. They may be single-sited, virtual, and distributed.” [4]. However, in this work, we called these concepts TERS (Technology Ecosystem for Research Support).

In computing, the first interactions of the researchers with the TERS for access to resources and services were through the command-line interface [2]. This type of interface often makes it challenging to perform complex tasks due to its low usability level, especially in people with little computer training. In contrast, it is currently possible to use consolidated graphical user interfaces in the so-called Science Gateway (SG). These SGs define as “web-based enterprise information systems that provide scientists with customized and easy access to community-specific data collections, computational tools, and collaborative services on e-Infrastructures” [5, 6].

Although many SGs have proven to be of great importance in research and education [7], their implementation in institutions does not guarantee adequate management of available IT resources and services. Therefore, in this paper, we present an analysis made from a systematic mapping study (SMS) with two goals. The first was to classify studies with information about frameworks, models, methodologies, processes, and good practices to manage IT resources and services applicable to the TERS. The second was to identify studies that show trends in technological tools with a science gateway approach for TERS.

The rest of the document is structured as follows: Section 2 indicates the motivation for this work. Section 3 presents related works. Section 4 describes the method used to carry out the SMS. Section 5 contains the analysis and discussion of the work done. Section 6 discusses the threats to validity, and finally, Section 7 presents the conclusions.

2 Motivation

Many of the current scientific advances are supported mainly by computer technology represented in the TERSs [2]. These technological ecosystems are generally present in higher education institutions. They have diverse capacities of resources and computer services, which is due, among other reasons, to the particularities of the goals and budgetary designations of each institution [2].

Due to these differences, several strategies and tools have been proposed to face the set of needs in IT management inside the TERSs. That situation produces many documents about how to implement and use these different strategies or tools.

Therefore, IT managers have the challenge to face a proliferation of documentation about processes and technologies related to research support [7].

Motivated by the above situation, we made this paper supported by the analysis of an SMS. This SMS had two goals. The first goal was to identify studies and classify them according to their relationship with frameworks, models, methodologies, processes, and good practices to manage IT resources and services applicable to the TERS. The second goal was to identify studies related to technological tools with an SG approach.

Therefore, this work provides the community with interest in this topic a set of taxonomically structured studies, becoming a tool for stakeholders to focus on those studies they consider relevant, perhaps contributing to decision making or the adoption of processes and implementation of technological tools with an SG approach.

3 Related Work

We did not evidence any SMS (between 2016 and 2020) with the same goals set in this work in preliminary searches. However, we identified some related studies as the following:

- Afgan et al. in 2016 [8] describe several deployment models for technical solutions that favor the use of virtual laboratories as software services immersed in cloud computing environments.
- Gesing et al. in 2017 [9] describe how the Science Gateway Community Institute addresses various

challenges related to SGs through consultancy, strategies, and the use of specialized software with an SG focus.

- Netto et al. in 2018 [10] present a review and taxonomy of HPC clouds and include an overview of the challenges ahead in the scientific field.
- López García et al. in 2018 [11] present a discussion about the main challenges in programming and resource allocation for any infrastructure that supports scientific applications.
- Gesing et al. in 2018 [12] show the general architecture of SGs considering criteria to design SGs efficiently.
- Stewart et al. in 2019 [2] focus their attention on cyber-infrastructure and issues related to SGs and campus bridges, the future challenges of cyber-infrastructure, in addition to analyzing the challenges and opportunities related to the evolution of cyber-infrastructure and cloud computing.
- Barker et al. in 2019 [5] focus on exploring the global impact achieved by SGs in increasing research.
- Gesing et al. in 2019 [7] describe the challenges SG creators may face and their sustainability through campus teams.
- Martin et al. in 2019 [13] examine some challenges related to the unification of a metadata catalog of data products and other resources provided by multiple research infrastructures.

Although the works listed above represent a significant contribution in this area, none of them satisfy the goals proposed in this work. Because of this, we consider the construction of the SMS presented in this work.

4 Review Method

To achieve the goals proposed in this paper, we used the methodological guidelines indicated in the works of [14, 15] to build an evidence-based SMS (Systematic Mapping Study).

According to the studies [16, 17], it is possible to use a hybrid search strategy to construct an SMS. Thus, we combined two search strategies to realize the SMS involved in this work, one automatic and one manual. For building our SMS, we use an example the Ali et al. [18] for its pragmatism and clarity.

Furthermore, we support our process of building this SMS with the SMS-Builder software tool. This software is a web application that we created to help researchers to follow a SMS building process. SMS-Builder covers six stages of the SMS building process 1) Planning, 2) Study search, 3) Quality analysis, 4) Data collection, 5) Study analysis and classification, and 6) Results. In our case, we use SMS-Builder for recording, processing, analyzing, and evaluating SMS studies [19]. We release the SMS-Builder as Free Software with GPL v3 license. The source of SMS-Builder is available from <https://github.com/grid-ug/sms-builder> [19].

Therefore, in our work, we followed an adaptation of the protocol proposed by [14], which includes six stages. See Fig. 1.

4.1 Stage 1: Planning

At this stage, we established the general purpose of the research and defined goals, research questions, metrics, classification topics, inclusion/exclusion criteria, and quality criteria. See Fig. 2.

For the components “Study goals,” “Research Questions,” and “Metrics” of the planning stage, we apply the GQM model (Goal-Question-Metric) [20, 21]. These components consider the conceptual, operational, and quantitative levels, respectively.

4.1.1 Study Goals

Bearing in mind the aspects described in the section on motivation, we have defined two goals for the study detailed in Table 1.

Fig. 1 Stages of the process for the construction of an SMS

Fig. 2 Components of the planning stage

4.1.2 Research Question

For the construction of the RQs (Research Question), we use GQM and PICOC models [22, 23]. This model allows us to establish the aspects “Population,” “Intervention,” “Comparison,” “Outcomes,” and “Context,” which serve to situate the work to be done. See Table 2.

Keeping in mind the information from the PICOC, we defined two RQs. See Table 3.

4.1.3 Metrics

We defined the SMS metrics using a quantitative approach according to our classification structure. The details of the metrics are in Table 4. The criteria determined limited the documents to the validity of five years, looking for actuality in the subject matter. In addition, the type was limited to primary studies seeking greater rigor in the peer review.

4.1.4 Topics

The RQs and the PICOC model served as the baseline for selecting the classification topics used in this work. The topics are the following: Framework, Model, Methodology, Process, Good practice, Project, Technological tool, and Case study. The definitions of

Table 1 Goals for the SMS

Goal	Description
G1	To Classify studies with information about frameworks, models, methodologies, processes, and good practices for the management of IT resources and services applicable to the TERS (Technology Ecosystem for Research Support).
G2	To Identify studies that show trends in technological tools with a science gateway approach for TERS.

all the indicated topics are according to the definitions indicated in the Cambridge dictionary [24].

4.1.5 Inclusion/Exclusion Criteria

The inclusion and exclusion criteria we defined for the study are in Table 5.

We defined this period (five years), seeking the timeliness of the studies. In addition, we limited the type of studies to journal articles, seeking greater rigor in peer review.

4.1.6 Quality Criteria

At the end of the planning stage, we have adopted three quality criteria.

The first quality criterion is an adaptation of the CVI (Content Value Index) [25, 26]. In this case, we judged the documents by identifying those most relevant to the SMS. We used a quantitative scale from 0 to 5 for this index, where 0 implies a low relationship of the studies with the SMS goals and 5 implies a high relationship. See formula (1). k is the

Table 2 Application of the PICOC model

Component	Description
Population	Studies related to good practices and reference models for management of computer resources and services.
Intervention	Identification of the set of good practices, processes and technologies.
Comparison	Identifying acceptance and success stories.
Outcomes	Studies with good practices, processes, procedures and technologies for IT service management for research technology ecosystems.
Context	Science gateway and technology ecosystem.

Table 3 Research questions defined for the SMS

Goal	RQs	Description	Motivation
G1	RQ1	What are the studies with information about frameworks, models, methodologies, processes, and good practices for IT resource and service management applicable to TERS?	Provide stakeholders with a list of studies related to frameworks, models, methodologies, processes, and best practices for managing IT resources and services in TERS.
G2	RQ2	What studies show technological tools with a SG (Science Gateway) approach that allows IT resources and service management in TERS?	Identify studies with information on technological tools with an SG approach and manage IT resources and services in the TERS.

odd total workers, $f(n)$ is the value assigned by the worker n .

$$CVI = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^k f(n)}{k} \quad (1)$$

The second quality criterion considers the number of citations of each study concerning publication age (A), which we call SCI (Study Citation Index). See formula (2). C is *Citations* between 2016 to 2020, and A is *Age* of study. With this formula, we seek to balance the citation of the studies. Thus, a citation in a paper from 2020 has a higher value than in a paper from 2016.

$$SCI = \frac{C}{A} \quad (2)$$

The third quality criterion we use corresponds to the relationship of the studies with the research questions; this we call IRRQ (Index of Relationship to Research Questions). See formula (3).

$$IRRQ = \frac{N}{2} \quad (3)$$

Table 4 Metrics defined in the SMS

Metric	Description
M1	The number of studies about IT service management frameworks (methodological frameworks).
M2	The number of studies about best practices identified for the management of IT services.
M3	The number of studies about technological tools (software) for IT service management.
M4	The number of studies about technological implementations with a science gateway approach.

N corresponds to the *Number* of RQs to which the study is related. This value is divided by *two* because it is the total of RQs.

4.2 Stage 2: Search for Studies

This stage presents the search strategy used in the SMS. This strategy will be defined and described in detail in the Subsections 4.2.1 - 4.2.4 (see Fig. 3).

The result of this stage was 168 studies obtained in this way. There were 131 studies by databases, by snowballing, there were 37 studies, and finally, by direct inclusion, there were three studies.

4.2.1 Defining the Search Strategy

For the construction of this SMS, we used a hybrid approach. With this approach, we seek to obtain a greater volume of studies indexed and coming from diverse sources, beyond the results provided by the digital libraries. In this sense, we combine two search strategies. The first strategy is “Database search,” and consists of performing an automated query in academic databases with indexing [27]. The second strategy is “Snowballing,” which consists of a manual process based on a set of base documents to locate more studies according to the references and citations in them [27, 28].

To support the process carried out in this SMS, we have used the following elements: a) Academic databases. b) Software that we developed in *Java Enterprise Edition* to manage the studies identified and generate the respective statistics called SMS-Builder [19]. c) Tools to support the management of references such as *Endnote*, *Mendeley*, and *Google Scholar*.

Table 5 Inclusion/Exclusion criteria

Category	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Field	Abstract, Title and keywords (If it's possible).	–
Publication type	Journal articles.	Conferences proceedings, Thesis and books chapters.
Area/Discipline	Management, Computer Science, and Information technology and Management.	Areas not related to management, Computer Science, and Information technology and Management.
Period	Between 2016 to 2020	Less than 2016.
Language	English.	–

4.2.2 Search Strategy 1: Databases

This strategy comprises two components. The first component is called “Study identification”. It focuses on establishing the keywords for constructing the search strings that lead to completing the queries in digital libraries. The second component is called “Study selection”. It focuses on applying various criteria to refine the search results of studies to select those with the most significant SMS value.

Study identification In order to ensure the feasibility of the SMS and by consensus of the authors, it was decided to limit the number of databases to six, including ACM, IEEE Explorer, Science Direct, Springer, Scopus, and Web of Science.

In this part of the process, it is necessary to establish the keywords used later in the search strings of

each of the databases. We again use the PICOC model as a methodological guide to identify key terms or phrases to fulfill this purpose. We refined these terms by including synonyms (See Table 6).

The main keywords we selected were “Management” and “Science Gateway.” To expand the research overview, we used the Boolean operator “OR” to add synonyms to the main keywords.

Finally, the set of keywords selected for the construction of the search string are in Table 7.

To direct the research towards the interception of these two groups of terms, the Boolean operator “AND” was used. Once we identified the keywords, we continued constructing the search strings for the digital libraries using an iterative process. The iterative construction of the search strings consists of performing a heuristic process with the keywords, synonyms, and related concepts by using disjunctions

Fig. 3 Activities of the study search stage

Table 6 Keywords identified using the PICOC model

Component	Keywords
Population	Management, Frameworks, good practices, Processes, Technologies.
Intervention	Identification (Set, Group, Part or Elements).
Comparison	Success stories, and Case study.
Outcomes	Set of frameworks, processes, tools, technologies, and good practices.
Context	Research technology ecosystem, Digital ecosystem, Enterprise ecosystem, and Computer science.

and conjunctions that conform to the syntactic rules of each database considered in the automatic search. Thus, these strings vary according to the characteristics and functions of each database. See Table 8.

After the search strings we built, we submitted them to each database engine. Table 9 shows the set of results obtained. We identified a total of 8,590 studies preliminarily, and it is worth noting that the Springer database contributed 84.16% of the results.

Study selection To refine the results obtained up to this point, we apply the inclusion and exclusion criteria defined in the planning phase. Table 10 shows the results of this step. We reduce the total number of studies to 418. According to the different databases consulted, Springer still has the most considerable contribution, with 43.30% of the studies.

From the 418 studies selected, we applied the exclusion of 69 studies because they were duplicates. After this elimination, now the studies included are 349. From this new set of data, we perform a review called “Screening,” this procedure consists of verifying the title, abstract, and keywords of each study to determine if they are in the context of the research, that is, if they are in the line indicated by the SMS goals. The screening process let us discard 218

Table 7 Database search keywords

Keywords	Synonyms and Related concepts
Management	Governance.
Science gateway	Virtual research environment, Virtual laboratories, Science DMZ, Research infrastructure, Computing resource sharing, and Computing service sharing.

studies because some of them made references to different fields and others focused on different ways, such as selling some commercial product.

Thus, we concluded the first search strategy with a total of 131 selected studies. Figure 4 shows an overview of the activities and results obtained in search strategy 1.

4.2.3 Search Strategy 2: Snowballing

Snowballing search strategy starts with identifying the base set of documents to be used, followed by a document review and selection. The review consists of verifying the list of references by identifying new documents (backward snowballing). Similarly, the documents that cite the revised document are identified (forward snowball), which requires using a database that indicates this information. In all cases, the document section applies the exclusion criteria apply [29].

This strategy comprises two steps. The first step is called “Snowball baseline building” and focuses on establishing studies to initiate reference and citation analysis. For the composition of this set of studies, we used various criteria based on the CVI (Content Value Index), SCI (Study Citation Index), besides also using direct inclusion. The second step is called “Study selection”, and it focuses on the analysis of references (Backward snowballing) and citations (Forward snowballing) of each study.

Snowball baseline building Based on the 131 selected studies, we evaluate the studies applying the quality criteria according to the CVI index. The result of this activity corresponds to 13 selected studies.

With the remaining 118 studies, we evaluated according to the quality criteria based on the SCI index.

Once we calculated the SCI index for all the studies, we carry out a frequency analysis to determine 25% of the studies with a higher SCI. The result of this analysis is equivalent to 30 studies chosen from the 118 considered.

As part of the process followed to make the SMS, it is possible to include studies directly. This direct inclusion allows flexibility in the method followed in considering studies outside the exclusion criteria. In our particular case, three studies of the proceedings type were included.

Table 8 Search strings for digital libraries

Database	Search Query	Field
ACM	Allfield:(("Management" OR "Governance") AND Abstract:(("science gateway" OR "Virtual research environment" OR "Virtual laboratories" OR "Science DMZ" OR "Research infrastructure" OR "Computing resource sharing" OR "Computing service sharing")))	All fields
IEEE Xplore	("All Metadata": "Management" OR "Governance") AND ("All Metadata": "science gateway" OR "Virtual research environment" OR "Virtual laboratories" OR "Science DMZ" OR "Research infrastructure" OR "Computing resource sharing" OR "Computing service sharing")	All Metadata
Science Direct	(Management OR Governance) AND ("science gateway" OR "Virtual research environment" OR "Virtual laboratories" OR "Science DMZ" OR "Research infrastructure" OR "Computing resource sharing" OR "Computing service sharing")	Title, Abstract, and Keywords
Scopus	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Management" OR "Governance") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("science gateway" OR "Virtual research environment" OR "Virtual laboratories" OR "Science DMZ" OR "Research infrastructure" OR "Computing resource sharing" OR "Computing service sharing") AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016)) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "COMP")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English"))	Title, abstract and keywords
Springer	(Management OR Governance) AND ("science gateway" OR "Virtual research environment" OR "Virtual laboratories" OR "Science DMZ" OR "Research infrastructure" OR "Computing resource sharing" OR "Computing service sharing")	All document
Web Of Science	TS=("management" OR "Governance") AND TS=("science gateway" OR "Virtual research environment" OR "Virtual laboratories" OR "Science DMZ" OR "Research infrastructure" OR "Computing resource sharing" OR "Computing service sharing")	Title, Abstract, and Keywords

Table 9 Results of search strings

Criteria	ACM	IEEE	Science Direct	Scopus	Springer	WoS	Total
Search string with keywords only	85	133	118	724	7229	301	8590
Percentage contribution	0,99%	1,55%	1,37%	8,43%	84,16%	3,50%	100%

Table 10 Summary of automatic search results with exclusion criteria

Criteria	ACM	IEEE	Science Direct	Scopus	Springer	WoS	Total
Search string with keywords only	3	6	47	43	181	138	418
Percentage contribution	0,72%	1,44%	11,24%	10,29%	43,30%	33,01%	100%

Fig. 4 Overview of the activities and results obtained in search strategy 1

The total of the studies identified by CVI (13), SCI (30), and direct inclusion (3) add up to 46 and constitute the baseline for the initiation of snowballing.

Study selection We started with a backward iteration reviewing in each of the 46 studies the existing references. This review allowed us to identify new articles that meet the inclusion requirements. The result was 14 new studies.

Later we did a forward iteration reviewing those studies that cite the baseline documents. This activity was done through Google Scholar and following the practice in the study [18]. The result of this activity was 20 new studies. In total, the snowballing search strategy allowed the identification of 37 studies, 34 of them through Forward-Backward iterations and three

studies that we integrated by direct inclusion. See Fig. 5.

4.2.4 Study Search Results

Finally, adding the 131 studies from the database search strategy and the 37 studies identified by the snowballing search strategy resulted in 168 studies. See Table 11.

4.3 Stage 3: Quality Assessment

According to [18], it is not necessary to incorporate a quality evaluation in an SMS. Nonetheless, a quality evaluation could bring the SMS closer to a systematic review [30]. Therefore, we sought to verify the

Fig. 5 Snowballing search strategy

relevance of the studies identified by the SMS goals through quality assessment. We use the CVI (Content Value Index), SCI (Study Citation Index), and IRRQ (Index of Relationship to Research Questions) defined in the planning stage to conduct the quality assessment.

4.3.1 Content Validity Assessment

This evaluation involved analyzing the content of the studies to determine their value to the research context. For this, we applied the CVI index described in the planning stage.

We perform the rating of the studies according to the CVI index with an odd number of evaluators. In this way, we avoid tying in the rating of this index since if there is an odd number of evaluators, a majority decision can always be made. Next, we conducted a frequency analysis to select the most significant quartile studies: those with a higher CVI.

We carried out twice this type of evaluation. The first time was selecting the studies that made part

of the baseline for the Snowballing search strategy. The second time was after identifying the 168 studies included in the SMS whose results are in Step 5: Classification of studies.

4.3.2 Index for Quality Assessment by the Number of Citations

This evaluation of the studies was done by us, keeping in mind the SCI index. We calculate this index supported by the SMS-Builder software [19] and the citation data indicated by Google Scholar. Next, we also perform a frequency analysis to select the most significant quartile studies: those with a higher SCI.

4.3.3 Index for the Evaluation of the Relationship of Studies to Research Questions

This quality assessment uses the IRRQ index described in the Planning stage (Section 4.1). In this sense, we analyzed the selected studies to establish their relationship to the classification topics. Besides, the topics also have a direct relationship with the research questions.

Through this process, we set the SMS-Builder software [19] to establish the direct relationship of the studies with the research questions proposed in this SMS. As in the previous cases, we also performed a frequency analysis where we selected the most significant quartile of studies, i.e., those with a higher IRRQ.

Table 11 Results of phase 2: Search for studies

Strategy	Studies	%
Databases	131	77,98%
Snowballing	37	22,02%
Total	168	100%

4.4 Stage 4: Data Extraction

After applying the procedures for the search and selection of studies and carrying out their quality assessment, we selected 168 primary studies. We labeled these studies with the prefix SPS (Selected Primary Study) followed by a number, and their list is in Table 12.

From the 168 SPSs, we design and fill in the forms to obtain relevant data from the SMS. The information contained in the SPSs is related to the research questions through the topics defined in the planning stage and consigned through the GQM and PICOC models. Also, we extracted some metadata such as keywords to identify underlying aspects of the SPSs.

Table 12 The 168 selected primary studies (SPSs)

Selected Primary Studies (SPSs)									
ID	Ref	ID	Ref	ID	Ref	ID	Ref	ID	Ref
SPS001	[31]	SPS002	[32]	SPS003	[33]	SPS004	[34]	SPS005	[35]
SPS006	[36]	SPS007	[37]	SPS008	[38]	SPS009	[39]	SPS010	[40]
SPS011	[41]	SPS012	[42]	SPS013	[43]	SPS014	[44]	SPS015	[45]
SPS016	[46]	SPS017	[47]	SPS018	[48]	SPS019	[49]	SPS020	[50]
SPS021	[51]	SPS022	[52]	SPS023	[53]	SPS024	[54]	SPS025	[55]
SPS026	[56]	SPS027	[57]	SPS028	[58]	SPS029	[59]	SPS030	[60]
SPS031	[61]	SPS032	[62]	SPS033	[63]	SPS034	[64]	SPS035	[65]
SPS036	[66]	SPS037	[67]	SPS038	[68]	SPS039	[69]	SPS040	[70]
SPS041	[71]	SPS042	[72]	SPS043	[73]	SPS044	[74]	SPS045	[75]
SPS046	[76]	SPS047	[77]	SPS048	[78]	SPS049	[79]	SPS050	[80]
SPS051	[81]	SPS052	[82]	SPS053	[83]	SPS054	[84]	SPS055	[85]
SPS056	[86]	SPS057	[87]	SPS058	[88]	SPS059	[12]	SPS060	[89]
SPS061	[90]	SPS062	[91]	SPS063	[5]	SPS064	[92]	SPS065	[93]
SPS066	[94]	SPS067	[95]	SPS068	[96]	SPS069	[97]	SPS070	[10]
SPS071	[98]	SPS072	[99]	SPS073	[100]	SPS074	[101]	SPS075	[102]
SPS076	[103]	SPS077	[104]	SPS078	[105]	SPS079	[106]	SPS080	[107]
SPS081	[108]	SPS082	[109]	SPS083	[110]	SPS084	[111]	SPS085	[112]
SPS086	[113]	SPS087	[114]	SPS088	[13]	SPS089	[115]	SPS090	[116]
SPS091	[117]	SPS092	[118]	SPS093	[119]	SPS094	[120]	SPS095	[121]
SPS096	[122]	SPS097	[123]	SPS098	[124]	SPS099	[125]	SPS100	[126]
SPS101	[127]	SPS102	[128]	SPS103	[129]	SPS104	[130]	SPS105	[131]
SPS106	[132]	SPS107	[133]	SPS108	[134]	SPS109	[135]	SPS110	[136]
SPS111	[137]	SPS112	[138]	SPS113	[139]	SPS114	[140]	SPS115	[141]
SPS116	[142]	SPS117	[143]	SPS118	[144]	SPS119	[145]	SPS120	[11]
SPS121	[146]	SPS122	[147]	SPS123	[148]	SPS124	[149]	SPS125	[150]
SPS126	[151]	SPS127	[152]	SPS128	[153]	SPS129	[154]	SPS130	[155]
SPS131	[156]	SPS132	[157]	SPS133	[158]	SPS134	[159]	SPS135	[160]
SPS136	[161]	SPS137	[162]	SPS138	[163]	SPS139	[164]	SPS140	[165]
SPS141	[166]	SPS142	[167]	SPS143	[168]	SPS144	[169]	SPS145	[170]
SPS146	[171]	SPS147	[172]	SPS148	[173]	SPS149	[174]	SPS150	[175]
SPS151	[176]	SPS152	[177]	SPS153	[178]	SPS154	[179]	SPS155	[180]
SPS156	[181]	SPS157	[182]	SPS158	[183]	SPS159	[184]	SPS160	[185]
SPS161	[186]	SPS162	[187]	SPS163	[188]	SPS164	[189]	SPS165	[190]
SPS166	[191]	SPS167	[192]	SPS168	[193]				

We support some sections of this process through different computer tools such as spreadsheets, specialized software for reference management such as *End-Note* and *Mendeley*, and *SMS-Builder* [19] to construct data analysis. We have published all the information about this SMS on the site [194]. Those interested can obtain a Docker container (<https://hub.docker.com/r/griduq/sms-science-gateway>) with a working SMS-Builder containing all the data used in this SMS. We are inviting readers to interact through this technological tool to obtain complementary information provided to this article.

4.5 Stage 5: Classification of Studies

The classification of SPSs, we did through the grouping of topics, as shown in Table 13. This table represents a summary of the studies that respond to the research questions RQ1 and RQ2. The grouping of studies through topics implies that the same SPS can be related to one or more topics, such as the case of SPS160 that appears related to the topics “Good practice,” “Technological tool,” and “Case study or project” simultaneously, which infers a relationship with RQ1 and RQ2 respectively.

After the first classification, we evaluated the SPSs considering the inclusion/exclusion criteria and the quality criteria such as the CVI, SCI, and IRRQ indexes. The criteria used for the analysis and classification of the SPSs coincide with the quality criteria. See Tables 14, 15, and 16.

4.6 Stage 6: Results

This section presents the information about the results obtained through the execution of the SMS search protocol. In this sense, we initially present the general description of the data corresponding to the SPSs. This description covers aspects such as the origin of the studies, year of publication, the search strategy used in their location, quality indices, the relationship with the research questions with their respective topics and the keywords. Finally, we present the description of a word cloud obtained from the keywords of the SPSs.

It is important to remember that the association among the SPSs with Topics was established through classification indicated in Section 4.5. Besides, the

RQs were associated too in an inherent way because the Topics have a specific structure inside the RQs. In the same sense, we identified the association among main keywords of the SMS with sections title, abstract, and keywords in all SPSs.

4.6.1 General Description of SPSs

The searching and filtering studies process led to the identification of 168 SPSs, as shown in Table 12. These SPSs come from digital library databases, which we identified in the SMS through different strategies. Figure 6 shows the number of studies identified through the various sources and the details of the database search and snowballing strategies. Regarding the source, 77.98% of the SPSs were located through the database search strategy, followed by snowballing with 20.24%. Finally, direct inclusion represents 1.79% of the 168 SPSs considered.

Regarding the database search strategy, Fig. 6 shows that of the 131 studies identified through this strategy, 92.37% of the SPSs come from the Science Direct, Springer, and Web of Science databases; the remaining 7.63% come from the ACM, IEEE, and Scopus databases. Based on the 34 SPSs identified by the snowballing search strategy, 58.82% were located by the forward, and 41.18% through the backward process.

Considering the relationship of SPSs to RQs (Research Question), Fig. 7 shows that 60.71% of SPSs are related to RQ1, while 77.98% of SPSs are related to RQ2.

Also, Fig. 7 shows it is possible to observe that 22.02% of the studies have exclusively related to RQ1; 39.29% of the studies have exclusively related to RQ2. Finally, 38.69% of the SPSs are related to RQ1 and RQ2 simultaneously.

Figure 8 shows the topics defined in the planning stage for each research question and the number of SPSs related to the topics in a non-exclusive way. It is essential to keep in mind that one SPS may be related to several topics simultaneously. In this sense, Fig. 8 shows the five topics related to RQ1, of which the topic “good practices” is the most frequent with 58.82%. In contrast, the topic with the lowest frequency is “Process,” with 10.78%.

Figure 8 also shows the two topics related to RQ2, in which the topic “case study or project” is the

Table 13 Classification of SPSs by topics and RQs

RQ	Topic	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
RQ1	Framework	SPS028 SPS050 SPS091 SPS118 SPS143	SPS021 SPS036 SPS073 SPS162	SPS010 SPS059 SPS115 SPS137 SPS165	SPS022 SPS061 SPS095 SPS130 SPS152 SPS161	SPS146
	Good practice	SPS001 SPS004 SPS045 SPS046 SPS050 SPS055 SPS057 SPS066 SPS072 SPS106 SPS108 SPS109 SPS112 SPS116 SPS119 SPS133 SPS141 SPS153	SPS017 SPS018 SPS048 SPS099 SPS107 SPS122 SPS125 SPS128 SPS131 SPS140 SPS164	SPS002 SPS024 SPS059 SPS074 SPS075 SPS093 SPS115 SPS145 SPS163	SPS009 SPS015 SPS033 SPS056 SPS063 SPS087 SPS088 SPS100 SPS102 SPS129 SPS144 SPS147 SPS149 SPS150 SPS152 SPS154 SPS158 SPS160 SPS166	SPS030 SPS052 SPS086
	Methodology	SPS043 SPS077 SPS124 SPS159	SPS038 SPS104 SPS105	SPS074 SPS127 SPS148	SPS019 SPS102 SPS111 SPS114 SPS144 SPS158 SPS161	
	Model	SPS028 SPS071 SPS081 SPS121 SPS143	SPS047 SPS079 SPS107 SPS138 SPS164	SPS035 SPS059 SPS070 SPS093 SPS110 SPS165	SPS029 SPS042 SPS097 SPS144 SPS152	
	Process	SPS046 SPS108 SPS124 SPS153 SPS157	SPS036 SPS079 SPS164	SPS002	SPS144 SPS158	
	RQ2	Case study or Project	SPS001 SPS003 SPS004 SPS008 SPS011 SPS040 SPS043 SPS045 SPS065 SPS076 SPS084 SPS101 SPS103 SPS108 SPS109 SPS112 SPS116 SPS117 SPS119 SPS132 SPS134 SPS135 SPS143 SPS153 SPS156	SPS005 SPS006 SPS007 SPS017 SPS018 SPS037 SPS041 SPS047 SPS048 SPS089 SPS092 SPS094 SPS104 SPS107 SPS125 SPS128 SPS131 SPS140 SPS142 SPS155	SPS031 SPS032 SPS034 SPS035 SPS069 SPS070 SPS075 SPS090 SPS098 SPS115 SPS123 SPS126 SPS127 SPS137 SPS145 SPS148	SPS012 SPS014 SPS020 SPS033 SPS039 SPS042 SPS053 SPS060 SPS062 SPS063 SPS067 SPS080 SPS082 SPS087 SPS088 SPS097 SPS100 SPS102 SPS113 SPS129 SPS130 SPS136 SPS149 SPS150 SPS151 SPS154 SPS160 SPS166 SPS168
Technological tool		SPS004 SPS008 SPS043 SPS045 SPS046 SPS050 SPS057 SPS064 SPS068 SPS077 SPS106 SPS135 SPS139 SPS141 SPS153 SPS157	SPS017 SPS018 SPS021 SPS023 SPS048 SPS049 SPS058 SPS073 SPS083 SPS094 SPS096 SPS099 SPS104 SPS105 SPS128 SPS164	SPS010 SPS027 SPS034 SPS054 SPS059 SPS075 SPS090 SPS093 SPS115 SPS120 SPS126 SPS163	SPS016 SPS026 SPS033 SPS039 SPS042 SPS044 SPS051 SPS060 SPS061 SPS063 SPS080 SPS085 SPS088 SPS097 SPS102 SPS111 SPS114 SPS152 SPS154 SPS158 SPS160 SPS166	SPS013

most frequent with 71.76%. In contrast, the topic with the lowest frequency is “technological tool” with 51.15%.

Consider that the research period includes studies from 2016 to early 2020; in this sense, Fig. 9 shows a decrease in the number of studies published since

Table 14 23 studies with the highest CVI index and classified by topics

RQ	Topic	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
RQ1	Framework	SPS050		SPS059	SPS061 SPS095 SPS152	
	Good practice	SPS046 SPS050 SPS106 SPS153	SPS017 SPS122 SPS128	SPS059 SPS075	SPS063 SPS088 SPS102 SPS152	
	Methodology	SPS043 SPS077 SPS124	SPS104 SPS105		SPS102 SPS114	
	Model		SPS079	SPS059	SPS152	
	Process	SPS046 SPS124 SPS153	SPS079			
RQ2	Case study or Project	SPS043 SPS153	SPS017 SPS104 SPS128	SPS075	SPS060 SPS063 SPS088 SPS102	
	Technological tool	SPS043 SPS046 SPS050 SPS077 SPS106 SPS153	SPS017 SPS104 SPS105 SPS128	SPS059 SPS075	SPS060 SPS061 SPS063 SPS088 SPS102 SPS114 SPS152	

2017, dropping from 47 SPSs published in 2016 to 28 SPSs published in 2018. See Fig. 9. In contrast, by 2019, there is an increase over 2016 with a total of 49 SPSs. The low number of SPSs in the year 2020 maybe because it corresponds to studies published up to the first quarter of 2020.

According to the SCI index, this SMS present in 2016 and 2017, the largest number of SPSs in the most representative quartile. Concerning the CVI index, the SMS shows regularity in the number of SPSs per year, except for 2018 and 2020. Considering the IRRQ index, the SMS indicates that no SPSs are recorded for 2020, perhaps because this study only contemplates the first quarter of the year. Otherwise, the years 2016 and 2019 register in the SMS, the highest number of SPSs directly correlated to the two RQs.

Figure 10 shows the number of SPSs classified by the research questions and including their respective topics, in addition to considering the quality indices.

In this sense, this study indicated that about RQ1, the topic “Process” registered the lowest number with 11 SPSs equivalent to 6.55% of the 168 SPSs. In contrast, the topic “Good practice” registered the highest number with 60 SPSs, equivalent to 35.71%. To RQ2, the topics “Technological tool,” and “Case study or project” reached a significant number with 67 and 94 SPSs equivalent to 39.88% and 55.95%, respectively.

Concerning the CVI, SCI, and IRRQ indexes, we identified the topics “Good practice,” “Technological tools,” and “Case study or project” as the categories that represent the largest number of SPSs.

Figure 11 shows a cross-analysis between SPSs, main keywords, and synonyms. For the keyword “Management,” the synonym “Governance” stands out, which allowed the identification of 85 SPSs. Concerning the keyword “Science Gateway,” the synonym “Research infrastructure” is highlighted, which allowed the identification of 61 SPSs. On the other

Table 15 40 studies were corresponding to 25% of the most relevant according to the SCI index

RQ	Topic	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
RQ1	Framework	SPS143	SPS162	SPS165		
	Good practice	SPS004 SPS108 SPS116	SPS018 SPS099 SPS125 SPS128 SPS131 SPS140	SPS002 SPS075 SPS093	SPS009 SPS063	SPS086
	Methodology		SPS104 SPS105			
	Model	SPS071 SPS081 SPS143		SPS070 SPS093 SPS165	SPS029	
	Process	SPS108		SPS002		
RQ2	Case study or Project	SPS004 SPS065 SPS108 SPS116 SPS117 SPS143	SPS005 SPS007 SPS018 SPS104 SPS125 SPS128 SPS131 SPS140	SPS070 SPS075	SPS060 SPS063	
	Technological tool	SPS004 SPS064 SPS068 SPS139	SPS018 SPS099 SPS104 SPS105 SPS128	SPS075 SPS093	SPS060 SPS063	

Table 16 65 studies that fully meet the IRRQ index

RQ	Topic	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
RQ1	Framework	SPS050 SPS143	SPS021 SPS073	SPS010 SPS059 SPS115 SPS137	SPS061 SPS130 SPS152	
	Good practice	SPS001 SPS004 SPS045 SPS046 SPS050 SPS057 SPS106 SPS108 SPS109 SPS112 SPS116 SPS119 SPS141 SPS153	SPS017 SPS018 SPS048 SPS099 SPS107 SPS125 SPS128 SPS131 SPS140 SPS164	SPS059 SPS075 SPS093 SPS115 SPS145 SPS163	SPS033 SPS063 SPS087 SPS088 SPS100 SPS102 SPS129 SPS149 SPS150 SPS152 SPS154 SPS158 SPS160 SPS166	
	Methodology	SPS043 SPS077	SPS104 SPS105	SPS127 SPS148	SPS102 SPS111 SPS114 SPS158	
	Models	SPS143	SPS047 SPS107 SPS164	SPS035 SPS059 SPS070 SPS093	SPS042 SPS097 SPS152	
	Process	SPS046 SPS108 SPS153 SPS157	SPS164		SPS158	
RQ2	Case study or Project	SPS001 SPS004 SPS043 SPS045 SPS108 SPS109 SPS112 SPS116 SPS119 SPS143 SPS153	SPS017 SPS018 SPS047 SPS048 SPS104 SPS107 SPS125 SPS128 SPS131 SPS140	SPS035 SPS070 SPS075 SPS115 SPS127 SPS137 SPS145 SPS148	SPS033 SPS042 SPS063 SPS087 SPS088 SPS097 SPS100 SPS102 SPS129 SPS130 SPS149 SPS150 SPS154 SPS160 SPS166	
	Technological tool	SPS004 SPS043 SPS045 SPS046 SPS050 SPS057 SPS077 SPS106 SPS141 SPS153 SPS157	SPS017 SPS018 SPS021 SPS048 SPS073 SPS099 SPS104 SPS105 SPS128 SPS164	SPS010 SPS059 SPS075 SPS093 SPS115 SPS163	SPS033 SPS042 SPS061 SPS063 SPS088 SPS097 SPS102 SPS111 SPS114 SPS152 SPS154 SPS158 SPS160 SPS166	

hand, the synonym “Science DMZ” had the lowest contribution to identifying SPSs.

4.6.2 Word Cloud Display

Another result obtained from the 168 SPSs of the SMS, is the construction of a word cloud. With this type of graphics, we seek to identify the use of words and concepts that collectively have the most significant frequency in a set of documents. Figure 12 shows the word cloud generated with the WordCloud tool, whose construction basis is the set of keywords with a frequency greater than 1 in the SPSs.

Among the most frequent keywords are “Science gateway,” “Cloud computing,” and “Research infrastructure,” whose contribution in the point cloud amounts to 21.34%. The second level of relevance in terms of the word cloud corresponds to “Data management,” “Big data,” “Cyberinfrastructure,” and “Virtual Research Environment,” which represent 9.88%. The third level of relevance in the terms corresponds to “Bioinformatics,” “Data sharing,” “E-infrastructure,” “Interoperability,” “Sustainability,” and “Workflows,” which is represented by 11.85%.

5 Analysis and Discussion

Our interest in identifying and classifying studies related to the management of resources and services in the TERSs (Technology Ecosystem for Research Support) has led us to present a taxonomic structure. Through this taxonomy, we contribute to the documentary organization of these topics. See Fig. 13. A way to use this taxonomy may be to facilitate decision making when carrying out management in the TERS.

As part of the analysis carried out in the current SMS, we have managed to identify cloud computing technology as a leading element. This information is an unexpected result that should be considered a fundamental axis for adopting methodological and technological aspects to implement SG (Science Gateway) technologies. In this sense, this SMS contains 41 SPSs (Selected Primary Study) with explicit reference to cloud computing technologies already in their title, abstract, or keywords, some of the most relevant being the following 13 SPSs: SPS043, SPS050, SPS059, SPS075, SPS077, SPS095, SPS102, SPS104, SPS105, SPS106, SPS114, SPS122, and SPS128. Below, we

Fig. 6 SPSs by source and database search strategy

briefly describe these SPSs and their relationship with cloud computing:

- *SPS043* describes the principles and concrete ways of integrating SGs with multi-cloud systems. In this study, cloud computing technology plays a fundamental role as the underlying element to integrate frameworks such as WSPGRADE/gUSE with the CloudBroker platform.
- *SPS050* shows the success of integrating the WSPGRADE/gUSE SG framework with the Hadoop parallel data processing solution. In this context and according to the analysis made in the study, cloud computing technology, thanks to its scalability and elasticity, is a suitable scenario for this type of integration, which can support parallel and massive applications for scientific analysis of Big Data.
- *SPS059* describes the general architecture of SGs and the criteria for their efficient construction. What this study shows allows us to infer that cloud computing technology, whether in public or private environments, offers significant advantages in the deployment of complex HPC research infrastructures or services available through high-speed networks.
- *SPS075* shows that the H2020 INDIGO-DataCloud project results provide the scientific community with tools and applications based on cloud technologies. In particular, this project extends the PaaS solutions to allow public and private electronic infrastructures to be available through inter-fertilization policies such as GEANT. This condition facilitates the execution of applications using containers deployed in the cloud.

Fig. 7 SPSs by RQs

- *SPS077* proposes the extension of a scientific workflow to make it infrastructure aware. In this way, it is possible to create and destroy the fly the cloud infrastructures necessary to execute a flow. In this proposal, cloud computing technologies play a leading role by allowing flexible and on-demand use of infrastructure elements as needed. The proposed work also presents the cloud service called Occopus, which allows integration with the SG WS-PGRADE/gUSE framework.
- *SPS095* shows an open-source framework for deploying elastic virtual clusters on elastic physical clusters, which allows the adaptation between the computing needs of applications and the energy efficiency of the underlying hardware. In

Fig. 8 SPSs by Topics

Fig. 9 SPSs by years and indexes

this proposal, cloud computing technologies provide the necessary elasticity elements to materialize the adaptation on demand that the framework makes between the computing needs and the consumption of physical resources.

- *SPS102* proposes a microservice-oriented methodology that allows scientific applications to run on a distributed orchestration platform like software containers. This methodology allows creating on-demand research environments and uses cloud computing technology as a fundamental component by providing the flexibility to build isolated and easily repeatable computing environments framed in the platform-as-a-service model. Also, this methodology preserves an agnostic perspective on the cloud provider.
- The *SPS104* is part of the INDIGO-DataCloud project and describes the methodological approach of orchestrating heterogeneous clouds used in the project. The methodology uses OpenStack software, the open standard OASIS Topology, and the TOSCA specification (Topology and Specification for Cloud Applications). It also provides consistency in application deployment by using virtual machines and Docker containers homogeneously and transparently. This study uses cloud technologies as a fundamental foundation by including IaaS, PaaS, and SaaS models throughout its methodological process, without coupling to any particular cloud provider. Instead of taking advantage of the heterogeneous nature that these cloud providers can transparently deliver.
- The *SPS105* presents an orchestration method based on affinity mechanisms to automate the

Fig. 10 Indexes by topic and RQs

deployment and management of high availability services in multi-zone and multi-cloud environments. In this work, cloud technologies are the essential input that seeks to be optimized through the proposed orchestration method, taking advantage of multi-zone and multi-cloud integration as the basis for achieving high levels of availability.

- The *SPS106* presents achievements, lessons learned, and software solutions that allow the scientific community to simplify the use of large-scale and distributed computing. These benefits are possible through SGs and the combination of Quality in Cloud and Grid (QCG) middleware. In this context, cloud computing technology constitutes an essential layer as a component of large-scale and distributed computing, whose use seeks to support the scientific community through software proposed at work. This software marks a

baseline for visual design and user experience in the implementation of SGs.

- In the *SPS114*, the general context is formed by cloud computing technologies. In this sense, the study presents a methodology through the abstraction of heterogeneous resources and hardware/software configurations. This methodology allows provisioning services to users with little computing experience. Additionally, the study proposes using a middleware that offers services based on a recommendation scheme to harmonize the requirements with the available resources.
- In the *SPS122*, Science Gateway Cloud is presented as an intermediary element between users of scientific applications and cloud providers. Through these applications, scientists can process diverse processes on heterogeneous cloud resources, and which seeks, among other aspects,

Fig. 11 SPSs by Keywords

a balance between service levels for users and the reduction of resource management costs.

- The *SPS128* is branded in the context of the serverless infrastructure represented in the FaaS (Function-as-a-Service) model and its applicability for executing scientific workflows, especially those with intensive use computing and data. In this study, cloud computing technology is certainly leading now with its FaaS service model, which has been positioning itself as a paradigm in using on-demand services in cloud environments.

From the above, we can infer that cloud computing technology is an underlying and fundamental element in implementing technology solutions with an SG approach. Likewise, it is relevant for scientific communities that their technological applications have

high availability deployments to meet their research goals. Having this in mind, we consider that studies such as *SPS105* and *SPS122* ratify those deployment models that achieve availability levels of 99,9999 must use not only cloud computing technology but must also carry out implementations that involve multiple clouds and multiple deployment zones. In this way, it is possible to reach the desired service level agreements to develop scientific applications provided in the TERS.

6 Threats to Validity

Some of the main limitations present in this study are related to aspects such as the following: 1) Bias in the process of selecting studies. 2) Errors made during

6.4 Errors in the Application of the Search Protocol

We perform this protocol through peer review to reduce possible errors in the execution of the search protocol. The first evaluator followed the research protocol, and the second inspected his work. In order to avoid manual data processing, we use the SMS-Builder software [19]. This software brought about a decrease in the probability of errors during the application of the search protocol.

7 Conclusions

This paper presents a systematic mapping of studies related to IT resources and services management in the TERS. The period for this research was between 2016 and 2020.

The SMS obtained 168 SPSs of a search strategy that combined automated procedures for consulting digital libraries and manual procedures for locating studies based on citations and references related to the documents.

In the SMS, we defined a classification scheme according to topics determined in the planning phase. This scheme presents the mapping information in statistical tables and graphs that help describe the data and the existing relationship with the research questions.

With the SMS realization, we were able to evidence the proliferation of studies related to IT resources and services management with an SG approach. This situation faces the stakeholders to the problem represented by the available volume of studies.

Therefore, after completing the SMS, we proposed a taxonomic scheme based on the classification scheme used in this work. The above to facilitate the structuring of the body of documentation in this area. This structure could contribute to decision-making to adopt processes and implementation of technological tools with an SG approach.

Beyond the results obtained in the SMS, we analyzed the studies exploring underlying information or trends. Thus, we were able to demonstrate a wide acceptance in the implementing SG solutions where there is a leading role of cloud computing. This

leading is relevant when considering adopting methodological and technological aspects to implement the SG approach in the TERSs.

As for future work, we hope to continue comparing some of the relevant technological tools to deploy test environments, looking for their behaviors in the TERSs.

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